

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY**

MASTER OF RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT MANAGEMENT

VINCENT PATALAY CEPILLO

**RESEARCH RESOURCE GENERATION IN HIGHER EDUCATION: PRACTICES
OF A PRIVATE INSTITUTION**

Thesis Adviser:

PROF. JEAN A. SALUDADEZ, PhD
Faculty of Management and Development Studies

15 August 2024

Permission is given for the following people to have access this thesis, subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the UP IPR policy and any contractual obligations:

Invention (I)	<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	or	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No
Publication (P)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Yes	or	<input type="checkbox"/>	No
Confidential (C)	<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	or	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No
Free (F)	<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	or	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No

Student's signature:
Thesis adviser signature:

University Permission Page

RESEARCH RESOURCE GENERATION IN HIGHER EDUCATION: PRACTICES OF A PRIVATE INSTITUTION

"I hereby grant the University of the Philippines a non-exclusive, worldwide, royalty-free license to reproduce, publish and publicly distribute copies of this Academic Work in whatever form subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the UP IPR policy and any contractual obligations, as well as more specific permission marking on the Title Page."

"I specifically allow the University to:

Specifically, I grant the following rights to the University:

- a. Upload a copy of the work in the theses database of the college/school/institute/department and in any other databases available on the public internet*
- b. Publish the work in the college/school/institute/department journal, both in print and electronic or digital format and online; and*
- c. Give open access to the work, thus allowing "fair use" of the work in accordance with the provision of the Intellectual Property Code of the Philippines (Republic Act No. 8293), especially for teaching, scholarly and research purposes.*

Vincent Patalay Cepillo and 08/15/2024
Signature over Student Name and Date

Acceptance Page:

This thesis titled: “**RESEARCH RESOURCE GENERATION IN HIGHER EDUCATION: PRACTICES OF A PRIVATE INSTITUTION**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for Master of Research and Development Management.

JEAN A. SALUDADEZ, PHD
Chair, Thesis Committee

31 October 2024
(Date)

PRIMO G. GARCIA, PHD
Member, Thesis Committee

11 November 2024
(Date)

MELINDA F. LUMANTA, PHD
Member, Thesis Committee

12 November 2024
(Date)

JOANE V. SERRANO, PHD
Dean
Faculty of Management and Development Studies

16 November 2024
(Date)

Biographical Sketch

The researcher and author of this study, entitled *Research Resource Generation in Higher Education: Practices of a Private Institution*, is **Mr. Vincent Patalay Cepillo**.

He is a native of the town of Tiaong in the Province of Quezon. Vincent was born on August 18, 1998, as eldest of the two children of Mr. Nicandro Papiro Cepillo, a retired and providing soldier, and Mrs. Narcisa Patalay Cepillo, a loving, caring and supportive mother.

He finished his elementary education at Bula Elementary School, graduating with honors, and completed his high school studies at Recto Memorial National High School, receiving the Vice President's Leadership Award from the Office of then Vice President of the Republic of the Philippines, Jejomar C. Binay. He earned his bachelor's degree in Accountancy from the San Pablo Colleges, in San Pablo City, Laguna, graduating *Magna Cum Laude*, and as an Outstanding Student Awardee and receiving the Excellence in Accounting and Excellence in Extra-Curricular Activities awards. He has also earned 18 units of the *Juris Doctor* program from the San Pablo Colleges – College of Law.

His passion includes literary writing, as a matter of fact, he was able to publish two books under the *Ukiyoto Publishing*. His first book was entitled *Statements of the Soul*, which is a collection of short English poems about love and life. The other book that he was able to publish was named *Vitae: mga tula at maikling kwento*, which is composed of Filipino poems and short stories about life.

Presently, he is working as the Executive Secretary to the President, Accounting Supervisor and Human Resource Officer of the Asian Institute of Technology and Education and Olinsterg College, Higher Education Institutions in Tiaong, Quezon.

Acknowledgment

The researcher would like to recognize the people who have made this paper a tangible piece of reality.

Firstly, it is the researcher's desire to acknowledge the **Asian Institute of Technology and Education** for its unwavering support as he was endeavoring to accomplish this study. Special thanksgiving and appreciation are rendered to its School President, **Dr. Nilo S. Gret, CPA** for his benevolent and generous assistance and aid all throughout the researcher's scholarly journey in the University.

Acknowledgement is also due to **all the professors** of the researcher and to all the helping **staff** during his Master of Research and Development Management (MRDM) adventure. Their care, lessons and knowledge shared to him have sufficiently equipped him to be able to proceed and accomplish this research.

Gratitude is also invoked for the Thesis Adviser of the researcher, no less than, **Prof. Jean A. Saludadez, PhD**, for the enlightenment, comments, advice, support, knowledge and help that she has untiringly extended to develop and forge this paper, which was initially just an iota of idea of the researcher. True enough, this paper would have not come this far if not for Prof. Saludadez.

This paper would have not also ended up to be a documentation of pursued knowledge and wisdom if not for the guidance of the members of the researcher's Guidance Committee, hence, due recognition, as well, is extended to **Dr. Primo G. Garcia and Dr. Melinda F. Lumanta**, whose sharing of worthy information, queries and remarks has been immensely contributory to this triumphant endeavor.

Thanksgiving is also given to the researcher's family, the **Cepillo Family**, for without this unshakeable and solid support system, the former could have not strived and thrived during the most challenging days of this chapter in his academic career.

Finally, and of course, to **Almighty God**, the creator and giver of life, knowledge and wisdom, eternal and unending thanksgiving and acknowledgement is always devoted for You.

Dedication

This paper is dedicated to:

The Asian Institute of Technology and Education Research Center

The very unit that inspired the topic pondered in this paper and the people who have helped the creation of this paper, may the knowledge contained in this study be able to help it progress and develop.

The Asian Institute of Technology and Education and Its Management

May this paper be adequate to express the biggest of thank you for all your support and assistance during its development and production.

The Thesis Adviser

As the fruit of the collaborative and scholarly efforts of the Thesis Adviser, Dr. Jean A. Saludadez and the researcher, this paper is likewise dedicated to Doc Jean as a token of gratitude for her indefatigable exertions to make this work a reality.

The Cepillo Family

In return for your love, pride and affection, this is for you.

My Creator and God

For you have dedicated to me your life and love, may this fruit of our efforts, while can never be enough, be a representation of my dedication and passion to serve and love you.

Abstract

Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) are known to perform not only instructional or classroom-based functions but also in extending its efforts to develop the students into research and extension. Research, nowadays, has gathered so much relevance as it becomes part and one of the highlights of the educational system of the Philippines, let alone of the world. HEIs or colleges and universities in their curricula require students to submit and accomplish their research projects before being conferred with their respective degrees. This is much more of a requirement too in graduate schools. Educational Institutions also encourage and, sometimes, even require their faculty members to be engaged in research and development to contribute in the expansion of the institution. However, research activities and undertakings for an HEI is not without cost and requirements, hence the necessity to generate research resources. The studies and literatures available discuss the importance of research and the relevance of resources in conducting research. The issues and concerns for the lack of funds and the support of the institution towards research undertakings were also emphatically expounded on those literatures, however, there is no specific study yet which is directed as to the practices of and perspectives underlying the generation of resources of a Private Higher Education Institution to support and facilitate its research undertakings.

In carrying out the study, the researcher used as its framework, the ethnomethodological approach. This framework best fits the objective of the study, since ethnomethodology seeks to answers questions through the experiences of the actors, in this case, of the AITE Research Center, in using the methods or ways that they have been observing. The study conducted revolved in analyzing the different

practices or methods by which the AITE Research Center generates its funds and in understanding the different perspectives that fueled the practices observed by the Research Center. The purpose of the study also included the development of a model which fits the context of Private Higher Education Institutions in terms of generating research resources. Data were gathered from the AITE Research Center by obtaining pertinent documents like memoranda, minutes of meetings and budget documents. All documents were gathered with the consent of the school management. After gathering the documents were all gathered, they were textually analyzed and thematically presented in the paper with the end in mind of answering the research questions.

The results of the study revealed that the AITE-Research Center's research resource generation are: (1) allocation of school funds, (2) partnership with other HEIs and NGOs, and (3) application for government grants. In line with these practices, the perspectives that led the school management to allocate funds for the research activities of the AITE Research Center is its belief and realization that research indispensable in the development and learning of its students. Another reason why it is being so practiced is to fill up or cover the deficiency or lack in the funds generated from the other sources of research funds. For partnership with other HEIs and NGOs AITE Research Center is led to push for those because it takes as perspectives the facts that it can lead to collaborative research that can improve the quality and productivity of research. Likewise, these partnerships can also open ties and relationships aside from research-related connections, and it can also lessen the management's burden by augmenting the school allocation for the Research Center. As for applying for government grants, the AITE Research Center aside from being primarily driven by the fact that it can add up to the funds allocated by the school,

hence lessening the school's burden, also strives to avail those grants, to take advantage of the break fostered by the different agencies in supporting HEIs to level up its quality of education through research, and to also grab the opportunities available from and build relationship with those agencies not only regarding research but about other aspects of higher education, as well. A research resource generation model showing derived organizational strategies was also developed to aid and guide other Research and Development Organizations (RDOs) in gathering resources for their research activities.

Keywords: Research Resource, Resource Generation, Research and Development, Ethnomethodology, Higher Education Institution, Private Institution

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title Page	i
University Permission Page	ii
Acceptance Page	iii
Biographical Sketch	iv
Acknowledgment	v
Dedication	vii
ABSTRACT	viii
Table of Contents	xi
List of Tables	xiii
List of Figures	xiv
Chapter 1: The Research Problem	15
Resource Generation in R&D Process	15
Importance of Resource Generation as a Study	16
Chapter 2: Theoretical Background	17
Organizational and Institutional Resources	17
Resources of Educational Institutions for Research	18
Chapter 3: Research Framework and Research Questions	23
Research Framework	23
Research Questions	25
Chapter 4: Research Methodology	26
Study Site	26
Data Collection	26
Data Analysis	30
Chapter 5: Results and Discussion	54
Research Resource Generation Practices	54
Allocation of School Funds	54
Partnership with HEIs and NGOs	57
Application for Government Grants	60
Perspectives Underlying Research Resource Generation Practices	63
For Allocating School Funds	63
Indispensable Role of Research in the	

Development and Learning of the Students	64
Fill Up the Deficiency or Lack of Funds from Other Sources of Research Resources	65
For Partnering with other HEIs and NGOs	65
Improved Quality and Productivity of Research through Collaboration	66
Ties and Relationships, with Other HEIs and NGOs, aside from Research	67
Lessened Management Burden due to Additional Funds from Partnership with Other HEIs and NGOs	67
For Applying for Government Grants	68
Leveled-up Quality of Education through Research with Government Support	69
Opportunities from Government Agencies Regarding the Other Aspects of Higher Education	69
Lessened Management Burden due to Grants from Government	70
Research Resource Generation Model	72
Chapter 6: Research Summary, Conclusion and References	82
Research Summary	82
Conclusions	86
Recommendations	88
Future Studies	88
Practical Recommendations	89
References	91

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. Allocation of School Funds as a Research Resource Generation Practice of AITE Research Center	32
Table 2. Partnership with Other HEIs and NGOs as a Research Resource Generation Practice of AITE Research Center	38
Table 3. Application for Government Grants as a Research Resource Generation Practice of AITE Research Center	40
Table 4. Perspectives of AITE Research Center for Allocating School Funds	43
Table 5. Perspectives of AITE Research Center for Partnering with Other HEIs and NGOs	49
Table 6. Perspectives of AITE Research Center for Applying for Government Grants	50

LIST OF FIGURES

- Figure 1. Ethnomethodological Process of Data Collection and Analysis 28
Figure 2. Matrix of Organizational Strategies on Research Resource Generation 72

Chapter I

THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

Background of the Study

Resource Generation in Research and Development (R&D) Process

Every process requires resources in order to continue and operate. And this does not exempt R&D organizations (RDO) or units. A point of view to understand the generation of resources for R&D is that it means to acquire or accumulate funding to support the many programs and activities of the RDO. It can be said that resource generation is the commencement of the R&D process for without the resources gathered from this activity, a research project may not pursue. This is anchored from the fact that every R&D process indeed incurs expenses and costs.

This study is conducted at the Asian Institute of Technology – Research Center (Research Center), which is the research body of the Asian Institute of Technology and Education (AITE). AITE is a Higher Education Institution (HEI) located in Tiaong, Quezon Province which has been operating since 2009. And just like any other RDO the Research Center observes different practices and methods in gathering resources or funds to support its activities and programs.

The Research Center considers as the very first activity in its R&D process the security and acquisition of sufficient funds that will finance the various lined-up programs and activities that it has. It is only after funds have been gathered that research projects and programs can be allocated with certain targeted funding and thereafter proceed.

Importance of Resource Generation as a Study

Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), in general, are expected to participate actively in research endeavors, as it is the first and primary venue where students, faculty members and individuals are trained to conduct and even facilitate research undertakings. One feature also of every Higher Education Institution is for it not to be confined alone in instruction but to extend into activities that will help the institution to develop or grow, hence the necessity to have at least a research unit responsible for the said aim.

Given this indispensable importance of research in HEIs, it is also fitting to conduct an analysis of the practices that an HEI observes in generating funds to finance such research and the perspectives that entice those methods and ways. As pointed out, without sufficient resources a process will not move on. And here lies the very relevance of such a study. The fact that accumulation or procurement of funds marks the beginning or in other words provides for the continuity of every succeeding research activity is undeniably calling for a deeper understanding of research resource generation. By conducting a study regarding research resource generation, a deeper understanding of the different methods and approaches, or strategies, so to speak, to gather and raise funds to support research programs may be achieved. It is also equally important to have realizations as to the reasons or perspectives that call for the undertaking of those practices, since other RDOs or HEIs for that matter may be of the same situation as that of the HEI being studied. With that, different takes or points of view may be looked upon, considered and applied by other HEIs in order to generate resources.

Chapter II

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Review of Literature

Research is an important function of any educational institution, especially, of any higher education institution. Studies and literatures provide insights as to the background and salient nature of research as a unit of an HEI. A collection of the related literatures as to the role and function of research and how it works, together with the concerns on resources is provided hereto.

Research, especially these days and in this generation has become more significant. This is founded on the belief that through research, students will become more academically equipped and trained. As put by Hausman (2021), the created knowledge drives scientific and technological progress and spills over to the broader economy and society.

In the Philippines, doing research has become one of the important professional development programs for teachers that is emphasized by the Department of Education (DepEd) and the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) (Ulla M., 2017). The Higher Education Commission together with the Department of Education as the foremost academic education institutions claim that research is an indispensable activity that would be able to lead academic institutions to have better teachers or faculty members. And so, the importance of research to teachers also extend to the education institutions.

Organizational and Institutional Resources

Generally, institutions must prioritize activities that align with strategic key objectives and strike a balance between spending and ongoing commitments that they are comfortable with (Nnebedum & Egboka, 2017). School managements must underscore the needs of the schools by making development plans that are not burdensome on parents while also improving education (Tria, 2020). Research undertakings, in this regard, as they form part with the objectives of every higher education institution must also be taken as a priority.

Investment funds, payments, accounting, control models, economic calculations, and associated concerns, both inside and outside the institution, should be examined in terms of internal characteristics as well as probable effects, according to the document (Acido & Kilongkilong, 2022).

Negative status of the institution is a result of financial rationalization problems like the failure to make income internally and the misappropriation of available resources (Bua & Adzongo, 2014).

There are varying views regarding the resource allocation within an institution, and none can be called as the best practice, hence, no matter what approaches are used, the most important is that the resource is put in the appropriate department at the appropriate time (Acido & Kilongkilong, 2022).

Resources of Educational Institutions for Research

One of the general objectives of higher education is to rationalize higher education, increase internal and external efficiency, maximize resource usage, and generate more resources (CHED, 2016). With this, CHED further underscores the necessity for HEIs to implement a good resource handling even for research activities.

While, research has become more and more popular and relevant in the educational arena it is of no exemption to issues and concerns. One common challenge that teacher-researchers faced when doing research is the lack of support from the school. This lack of support refers to financial, work, and training support. Another challenge that teacher-researchers encountered when doing research was the lack of sufficient reference materials. Most of them revealed that their school have no updated library for current journals and books and no Internet connection for online searches (Ulla M. B., 2018).

According to Maglakelidze et al. (2013), there is no fixed rule on the manner financial resources must be directed to the education sector. But it has been studied that there is a direct relationship between research production and resources management, especially funding. There is a positive elasticity of scientific publications to university funding (Adams & Griliches, 1998).

Thelwall, et al (2023), discussed that a research undertaking may generate funds from their employer, a specialist research funding organization (e.g. government-sponsored or non-profit) or a research-needing organization.

One of the funding concerns for every HEI, which may extend to research activities is that without adequate financial resources, institutions cannot carry out their defined tasks effectively. Money must be available to run the different departments of the school (Yizengaw, Agegnehu, & Ehmke, 2021). Hence, it is only through funding that institutions will be able to sufficiently distribute resources (Acido & Kilongkilong, 2022).

Taking into account that much of the school budget for operations (90% and above) is allotted to salaries of teachers, the reason why research activities receive limited funds (Gonzalez, 2006).

Given CHED reports in 2000 which suggested that they having financed only 16 research projects with a total approved fund budget of about P9 million, it can be understood that many of the research conducted were not dependent on the small grants from CHED (Clemeña & Acosta, 2009).

Mbaleka (2015) contends that a few of the most challenging factors that hinder faculty members from not publishing enough or not publishing at all include having limited funds, and lack of institutional support.

Lack in internal financing is balanced by external funding. One of possible tool with respect to research undertakings is its external research collaboration. It is possible that an HEI's research products are a result of faculty research partnership with other HEIs and with financial support from government agencies (Quitoras & Abuso, 2021).

The issue of allotting resources to education institutions is multi-faceted (Etor et al., 2020). In the education setup, the resource allocation process is a mode used by the management to allocate and provide the resources available like learning materials, human resources, equipment, and funds to departments where they are most required to achieve the institution's goals (Acido & Kilongkilong, 2022).

Resource allocation process is particularly relevant since they have an immense impact on and influence on the many of other educational institution procedures (Jackson, Johnson, & Persico, 2016).

Resource control encompasses the processes that aid to assure that there will be efficiency and effectiveness in relation to the achievement of educational goals (Acido & Kilongkilong, 2022).

The top goals of resource control in educational setups are to put up short-term project proposals, know progress toward the plans, ensure synchronization among key aspects of the institution, delegate quantifiable duties to administrators without losing control, and deliver monitored versatility for dealing with short-term changes (Acido & Kilongkilong, 2022).

The studies and literatures available discuss the importance of research and the relevance of resources in conducting research. The issues and concerns for the lack of funds and the support of the institution towards research undertakings were also emphatically expounded. However, in the midst of these available and empirical

literatures, there is no specific study yet which is directed as to the practices of and perspectives underlying the generation of resources of a Private Higher Education Institution to support and facilitate its research undertakings.

Chapter III

RESEARCH FRAMEWORK AND RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Research Framework

The framework that guided the conduct of the study is ethnomethodology. In ethnomethodology, the researcher analyzes how people utilize social interaction to maintain an ongoing idea of reality in a particular situation (Corssman, 2019). Ethnomethodology primarily looks on the understanding of methods that people use in “doing” social life to mutually come up with recognizable interactions within a specific context, creating orderliness (Pillay, 2019).

According to Cuff et al., (2003) ethnomethodology tries to understand how a person’s social world (a world consisted by daily actions, objects and interactions) is developed, reached, and maintained and what this social world looks like from the point of view situated within it. In this view, researchers following ethnomethodology are mostly interested in means and ways that members utilize in their actual interactions and actions to understand and make sense of their situations and to respond on them (Heritage, Garfinkel and Ethnomethodology, 1996).

Ethnomethodology is linked and aligned with the concepts of reflexivity, indexicality, stock of knowledge, documentary method of interpretation, typifications and accountability. And that at its core, it is viewing social life as being undertaken through written and spoken language (Coulon, 1995). It is believed that in ethnomethodology the language use, as well as actions, are set socially, their meaning

are relative and united with known knowledge or the characteristics of the context in which they were used (Pollner & Emerson, 2001).

Heritage (1998) suggests that ethnomethodology begins from the idea that members have background knowledge about the situations being considered and taken into account in dealing with others.

Ethnomethodology conforms with the thought that things are understood in the moment, and in their own context, and that documents both reflect and create aspects of the social world (Hak, 1992). Hence, according to Garfinkel and Bittner (1999), it focuses on the relations that appear between social order and documents that make and are made by the documents. Further, with a pervasive, natural and social attitude, documents are taken as sources that are merely out there, ready to be utilized. And so, therefore, documents are seen as “intersubjective facts that are independent of any one person’s perception or action.” Documents are also known to have senses that are available for competent individuals to comprehend (Leiter, 1980).

It is said that in ethnomethodology, the idea of correct reading of documents holds correctly for the people involved in the construction of the documents and for those who subsequently get involved with those documents (Trace, 2016). Heritage (1996) suggested that what the document actually reflects is understood in an interpretive process in which it is differentiated with ‘what is known’. This framework also presents that documents give ways through which individuals can inscribe the accountability of their undertakings and it is through these descriptions and accounts that order in society is met and made achievable (Trace, 2016).

Trace elucidated that ethnomethodology begins from the idea that people have an innate attitude towards their experiences and make it possible and reasonable for them to act accordingly. With this idea, documents become a part of the ethnomethodological and everyday processes of action and interaction (Trace, 2016). And so, studies that use ethnomethodological approach need to imbibe a commitment to certain immersing methodological approaches and investigative tendencies (Lynch, 2009). In an organizational setup, any study of document works and documents itself must hence, involve a thorough examination of the practical details of everyday activities, which include work processes, institutional conversations, the organization of interactions and the way the members make decisions (Trace, 2016).

Research Questions

In order to understand the practices of a private higher education institution regarding its resource generation for its research undertakings, the study seeks to answer the question on how does PHEI accomplish resource generation as an organizational task, specifically the following research questions, *viz*:

1. What are the research resources generation practices of a private higher education institution (PHEI)?
2. What perspectives underlie PHEI's research resources generation practices?
3. What model of research resource generation in the context of Private HEI can be developed and proposed?

Chapter IV

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Study Site

The study was conducted at the Asian Institute of Technology and Education, a Higher Education Institution in Tiaong, Quezon, specifically at its research and development body, also called as the AITE Research Center. It was chosen as an HEI which practices different research resource generation practices.

Data Collection

The study utilized qualitative research design, specifically ethnomethodological research with the aid of textual analysis of pertinent documents. Garfinkel glanced at documentary method of interpretation to realize and know how individuals operate in situations that are basically indexical – ethnomethodological (Lehn, Harold Garfinkel: *The Creation and Development of Ethnomethodology*, 2014). The documentary method of interpretation warrants that instead of taking an already known idea of the meaning of an activity, individuals are said to look for and utilize patterns to create an image to understand reasons and meanings and motive in the behavior of other people. Documentary method of ethnomethodological framework calls for understanding meaning by taking an action as a “document” or as an expression of an underlying pattern that is taken from a person’s knowledge and experience (Garfinkel & Bittner, *Good’ organizational reasons for ‘bad’ clinic records*, 1999). In this view, and from a researcher’s perspective, actions can be understood and studied as a form of

document, such that it refers to pointers or evidence to certain underlying patterns that lead to social interaction possible (Garcia, Dawes, Kohne, Miller, & Groschwitz, 2006).

Since the study pondered on the methods and processes used by the Asian Institute of Technology and Education – Research Center to generate resources, it is fitted to use a design which will observe and identify the experiences of the people involved in the resource generation of the research unit. Ethnomethodological approach also befits the study since aside from being a framework, ethnomethodology is likewise inclined in answering queries as to the methods and procedures of the study subject, which in this case is delivered by textually analyzing the documents relevant to the research resource generation practices and perspectives of AITE Research Center.

As such and in order to achieve the goal of the study the following steps are expected to be implemented and undertaken, *viz*:

Figure 1. Ethnomethodological Process of Data Collection and Analysis.

Consent from the School Management

Since the study's data will particularly come from the minutes of meetings and memoranda of the Higher Education Institution, the Asian Institute of Technology and Education, it is necessary and indispensable that the school management gives its

permission to view, utilize and analyze the said documents for the purpose of this research.

In this view, the researcher will be writing a request letter addressed to the School President and through the Research Director to have copies of the transcripts of the meetings and memoranda which included in its agenda, the discussions regarding the research resource generation practices and activities of its research unit, the AITE-Research Center. The request will also extend to the analysis and evaluation of the said documents.

Given that the initiatives for research resource generation and allocation for the Research Center come from the school management, either directly or with the recommendation of the Research Director, the consent and permission of the former will not only be ethical but likewise instrumental as an outset in analyzing the practices of the institution regarding research resource generation.

Obtaining Copies of the Documents

When the researcher is already able to secure the consent and permission of the management, the researcher will then proceed to the gathering of the documents concerning and relating to research resource generation of the institution which are to be analyzed, specifically: (a) minutes of meetings and (b) memoranda.

The said documents can be accessed either through the Office of the School President, which is represented by the Executive Secretary to the President and/or

through the Research Director. The researcher will only take copies of, utilize and analyze the documents which make mention, discuss and relate to the research resource generation practice of the institution. Other subject matters of the documents which do not, in anyway, relate or partake on the practices of research resource generation of the Research Center will not be touched, for purposes of confidentiality and in consideration of the principle of relevance and plausibility.

Data Analysis

To facilitate the ethnomethodological approach in this study, the researcher has undertaken textual analysis of the pertinent documents of the AITE Research Center. Textual analysis of existing documents particularly of the minutes of the meetings and memoranda of AITE relating and concerning research resource generation, was conducted to gather data in order to fill the research gap and answer the research questions.

Textual Analysis of the Documents

In the study of Frey, Botan and Kreps (1999), they mentioned that the objective of Textual Analysis is to describe the contents, functions and structures of the messages contained in a text. Agreeably, Khan (2023), elucidated that textual analysis is a research methodology that critically and closely examines written, spoken or visual messages. Further, it is said that the center of textual analysis lies in the interpretation, comprehension and contextual understanding of the text (Khan, 2023).

The first three stages involved in the process of textual analysis (Khan, 2023), are as follows:

1. Descriptive Stage – in this study it would involve the thorough and close reading of the minutes of meetings and memoranda which relate to research resource generation practices of the institution. At this stage, the researcher would be able to both summarize the text and immerse himself to the tenor and perspective contained in the document.

2. Analytical Stage – within this stage, the researcher would be able to look at the moods, patterns and themes contained in the documents as to the practices of the institution on research resource generation. At this point, the researcher would be in a position to draw inferences and interpret the meanings of direct messages contained in the texts.

3. Interpretive Stage – the researcher after analyzing the minutes of meetings and memoranda would be able to surface out and discover the underlying meanings, the implied messages and even probably, symbolisms, contained in the documents.

With textual analysis and the observation of its stages, and given that the subject institution is a private higher education one, which generally generates all its funds from its own operations, the documents, namely: (a) minutes of meetings and (b) memoranda, when analyzed carefully and thoroughly, would indeed reveal the practices and the perspectives of the institution as to research resource generation.

The following analyses were utilized in order to answer the research questions of the study. It derived excerpts from the official documents provided by the AITE

Research Center. And from those excerpts, codes were established to come up with subthemes and themes. With this process, identification and deeper understanding of the patterns in the practices of the AITE Research Center along with its perspectives regarding resource generation were achieved.

Table 1.

Allocation of School Funds as a Research Resource Generation Practice of AITE Research Center

Quotation	Codes	Subthemes	Themes
“The school management takes it as a relevant step to allocate funds for the student, faculty and institutional research to be conducted and published by the Center.”	School management takes it as relevant step School management to allocate funds	School Management Action School Funding	Allocating School Fund
“The allocation shall be sourced by AITE from the Tuition and Other Fees paid by the students.”	Allocation shall be sourced by AITE Allocation shall be from Tuition and Other Fees paid by students	Source of Allocation	Allocating School Fund

<p>“The amount to be allocated will be relative to the available school fees collected from the students.”</p>	<p>Amount to be allocated</p>	<p>Amount of Allocation</p>	<p>Allocating School Fund</p>
<p>“While our school provides for the deficiencies in the budget expected to have been sourced from outside parties . . .”</p>	<p>School provides deficiencies in the budget from outside parties</p>	<p>School Management Action Research Funding</p>	<p>Allocating School Fund</p>
<p>“Given . . . the unavailability of funds from other sources, we would like to request that the Annual Research Budget for AY 2020-2021 be allocated with School Funds . . .”</p>	<p>Unavailability of funds from other sources Annual Research Budget be allocated with School Funds for AY 2020-2021</p>	<p>Research Funding</p>	<p>Allocating School Fund</p>
<p>“Given the unavailability of funds</p>	<p>Unavailability of funds from other</p>	<p>Research Funding</p>	<p>Allocating School Fund</p>

from other sources	sources than	School
than school fund	school fund	Management
allocation, it is hereby	allocation	Action
ordered for the		
Accounting and	Accounting and	
Finance Department	Finance	
to set aside the funds	Department to set	
[for] the Annual	aside funds for AY	
Research Budget for	2020-2021	
AY 2020-2021.”		

“Given the	Unavailability of	Research Funding	Allocating
unavailability of funds	funds from other		School Fund
from other sources	sources than	School	
than school fund	school fund	Management	
allocation, it is hereby	allocation	Action	
ordered for the			
Accounting and	Accounting and		
Finance Department	Finance		
to set aside the funds	Department to set		
[for] the Annual	aside funds for AY		
Research Budget for	2021-2022		
AY 2021-2022.”			

“Given the	Unavailability of	Research Funding	Allocating
unavailability of funds	funds from other		School Fund
from other sources	sources than		

than school fund	school fund	School	
allocation, it is hereby	allocation	Management	
ordered for the		Action	
Accounting and	Accounting and		
Finance Department	Finance		
to set aside the funds	Department to set		
[for] the Annual	aside funds for AY		
Research Budget for	2022-2023		
AY 2022-2023.”			

“Given the	Unavailability of	Research Funding	Allocating
unavailability of funds	funds from other		School Fund
from other sources	sources than	School	
than school fund	school fund	Management	
allocation, it is hereby	allocation	Action	
ordered for the			
Accounting and	Accounting and		
Finance Department	Finance		
to set aside the funds	Department to set		
[for] the Annual	aside funds for AY		
Research Budget for	2023-2024		
AY 2023-2024.”			

“The unavailability of	Unavailability of	Research Funding	Allocating
gathered funds from	gathered funds		School Fund
government grants	from government		
and partnerships with	grants and		

other HEIs and partnerships with
 NGOs has led the other HEIs and
 allocation of school NGOs
 funds to cover all the
 needed budget of the Led the allocation
 AITE Research of school funds to
 Center for SY 2019- cover the needed
 2020.” budget for AY
 2019-2020

<p>“The unavailability of gathered funds from government grants and partnerships with other HEIs and NGOs has led the allocation of school funds to cover all the needed budget of the AITE Research Center for SY 2020-2021.”</p>	<p>Unavailability of gathered funds from government grants and partnerships with other HEIs and NGOs</p> <p>Led the allocation of school funds to cover the needed budget for AY 2020-2021</p>	<p>Research Funding</p>	<p>Allocating School Fund</p>
--	--	-------------------------	-------------------------------

<p>“The unavailability of gathered funds from government grants</p>	<p>Unavailability of gathered funds from government</p>	<p>Research Funding</p>	<p>Allocating School Fund</p>
---	---	-------------------------	-------------------------------

and partnerships with grants and other HEIs and partnerships with NGOs has led the other HEIs and allocation of school NGOs funds to cover all the needed budget of the Led the allocation AITE Research of school funds to Center for SY 2021- cover the needed 2022.” budget for AY 2021-2022

<p>“The unavailability of gathered funds from government grants and partnerships with other HEIs and NGOs has led the allocation of school funds to cover all the needed budget of the AITE Research Center for SY 2022-2023.”</p>	<p>Unavailability of gathered funds from government grants and partnerships with other HEIs and NGOs</p> <p>Led the allocation of school funds to cover the needed budget for AY 2022-2023</p>	<p>Research Funding</p>	<p>Allocating School Fund</p>
--	--	-------------------------	-------------------------------

<p>“The unavailability of gathered funds from</p>	<p>Unavailability of gathered funds</p>	<p>Research Funding</p>	<p>Allocating School Fund</p>
---	---	-------------------------	-------------------------------

government grants	from government
and partnerships with	grants and
other HEIs and	partnerships with
NGOs has led the	other HEIs and
allocation of school	NGOs
funds to cover all the	
needed budget of the	Led the allocation
AITE Research	of school funds to
Center for SY 2023-	cover the needed
2024.”	budget for AY
	2023-2024

Table 2.

Partnership with Other HEIs and NGOs as a Research Resource Generation Practice of AITE Research Center

Quotation	Codes	Subthemes	Themes
“The AITE Research Center must open itself to partnership with other HEIs or even with NGOs who are willing to enter into a collaborative research activity.”	Open Collaborative	Research Center Action Research Funding	Partnering with HEIs and NGOs

<p>“I would like to encourage you (Research Director) to extensively undertake efforts to enter into various communications with other HEIs, NGOs... ..”</p>	<p>Extensively undertake efforts</p> <p>Various communications</p> <p>HEIs</p> <p>NGOs</p>	<p>Research Center Action</p> <p>Research Center Action</p> <p>Prospective Partners</p>	<p>Partnering with HEIs and NGOs</p>
--	--	---	--------------------------------------

<p>“... it would bring a great help, not only financially but also institutionally and socially, if we can have ties and relationships with other organizations . . .”</p>	<p>Not only financially</p> <p>Ties and relationships with other organizations</p>	<p>Impact of relationship</p> <p>Research Center Action</p>	<p>Partnering with HEIs and NGOs</p>
--	--	---	--------------------------------------

<p>“We are therefore expecting that portion of the Research Budget for the upcoming school year, 2020-2021 will come from other stated</p>	<p>Other stated sources of research funds</p>	<p>Research Funding</p>	<p>Partnering with HEIs and NGOs</p>
--	---	-------------------------	--------------------------------------

Sources of Research

Funds . . .”

“After the AITE Research Center’s efforts to communicate and attempts to enter into different research partnerships with outside parties, like other HEIs, NGOs....”	After efforts to communicate and enter into research partnerships	Research Center Action	Partnering with HEIs and NGOs
	HEIs	Prospective Partners	
	NGOs		

Table 3.

Application for Government Grants as a Research Resource Generation Practice of AITE Research Center

Quotation	Codes	Subthemes	Themes
“The AITE Research Center shall extend its efforts to apply and request for grants from government agencies, especially those highly related in	Extend its efforts Applying and requesting for grants from government agencies	Research Center Action Government Funding	Applying for Government Grant

education.”

“Whatever research grant will be received from government agencies will be distributed equally to the different programs of AITE, unless specified or intended by the granting agency.”	Will be distributed equally	Amount of Grant	Applying for Government Grant
---	-----------------------------	-----------------	-------------------------------

“I would like to encourage you (Research Director) to extensively undertake efforts to enter into various communications with other HEIs, NGOs and even with sponsoring government	Extensively undertake efforts	Research Center Action	Applying for Government Grant
	Various communications	Prospective Partners	
	Sponsoring government agencies		

agencies.”

“ . . . it would bring a great help, not only financially but also institutionally and socially, if we can have ties and relationships with other organizations . . . ”	Not only financially Ties and relationships with other organizations	Impact of relationship Research Center Action	Applying for Government Grant
---	---	--	----------------------------------

“We are therefore expecting that portion of the Research Budget for the upcoming school year, 2020- 2021 will come from other stated Sources of Research Funds . . .”	Other stated sources of research funds	Research Funding	Applying for Government Grant
---	--	------------------	----------------------------------

“After the AITE Research Center’s efforts to communicate and	After efforts to communicate and enter into	Research Center Action	Applying for Government Grant
---	---	---------------------------	----------------------------------

attempts to enter	research	Prospective
into different	partnerships	Partners
research	Government	
partnerships with	agencies	
outside parties,		
like other HEIs,		
NGOs and		
government		
agencies. . .”		

Table 4.

Perspectives of AITE Research Center for Allocating School Funds

Quotation	Codes	Subthemes	Themes
“The allotment of funds will be done in order to foster a research-conducive environment for students and faculty members alike.”	Allotment of funds Research-conducive environment for students and faculty	Allocating School Fund	Indispensable role of research in the development and learning of the students
“The Asian Institute of Technology and Education (AITE), at the peak of its aims, intently includes in	peak of AITE’s aims develop the full potential of its students	Allocating School Fund	Indispensable role of research in the development

the pursuit of its maximization of and learning of
mission to strive to research and the students
develop the full development
potentials of its
students and help
them become
achievers in their
chosen fields, the
role and
maximization of
research and
development”

<p>“Given the unavailability of funds from other sources than school fund allocation, it is hereby ordered for the Accounting and Finance Department to set aside the funds [for] the Annual Research Budget for AY 2020-2021.”</p>	<p>Unavailability of funds Accounting and Finance Department to set aside funds for AY 2020-2021</p>	<p>Allocating School Fund</p>	<p>Filling-up the deficiencies or lack of gathered funds from the other sources of research resources</p>
---	---	-------------------------------	---

“Given the unavailability of funds from other sources than school fund allocation, it is hereby ordered for the Accounting and Finance Department to set aside the funds [for] the Annual Research Budget for AY 2021-2022.”	Unavailability of funds Accounting and Finance Department to set aside funds for AY 2021-2022	Allocating School Fund	Filling-up the deficiencies or lack of gathered funds from the other sources of research resources
--	---	------------------------	--

“Given the unavailability of funds from other sources than school fund allocation, it is hereby ordered for the Accounting and Finance Department to set aside the funds [for] the Annual Research Budget for AY 2022-2023.”	Unavailability of funds Accounting and Finance Department to set aside funds for AY 2022-2023	Allocating School Fund	Filling-up the deficiencies or lack of gathered funds from the other sources of research resources
--	---	------------------------	--

<p>“Given the unavailability of funds from other sources than school fund allocation, it is hereby ordered for the Accounting and Finance Department to set aside the funds [for] the Annual Research Budget for AY 2023-2024.”</p>	<p>Unavailability of funds</p> <p>Accounting and Finance Department to set aside funds for AY 2023-2024</p>	<p>Allocating School Fund</p>	<p>Filling-up the deficiencies or lack of gathered funds from the other sources of research resources</p>
---	---	-------------------------------	---

<p>“The unavailability of gathered funds from government grants and partnerships with other HEIs and NGOs has led the allocation of school funds to cover all the needed budget of the AITE Research Center for SY 2019-2020.”</p>	<p>Unavailability of gathered funds</p> <p>Led the allocation of school funds to cover the needed budget for AY 2019-2020</p>	<p>Allocating School Fund</p>	<p>Filling-up the deficiencies or lack of gathered funds from the other sources of research resources</p>
--	---	-------------------------------	---

<p>“The unavailability of gathered funds from government grants and partnerships with other HEIs and NGOs has led the allocation of school funds to cover all the needed budget of the AITE Research Center for SY 2020-2021.”</p>	<p>Unavailability of gathered funds</p> <p>Led the allocation of school funds to cover the needed budget for AY 2020-2021</p>	<p>Allocating School Fund</p>	<p>Filling-up the deficiencies or lack of gathered funds from the other sources of research resources</p>
--	---	-------------------------------	---

<p>“The unavailability of gathered funds from government grants and partnerships with other HEIs and NGOs has led the allocation of school funds to cover all the needed budget of the AITE Research Center for SY 2021-2022.”</p>	<p>Unavailability of gathered funds</p> <p>Led the allocation of school funds to cover the needed budget for AY 2021-2022</p>	<p>Allocating School Fund</p>	<p>Filling-up the deficiencies or lack of gathered funds from the other sources of research resources</p>
--	---	-------------------------------	---

<p>“The unavailability of gathered funds from government grants and partnerships with other HEIs and NGOs has led the allocation of school funds to cover all the needed budget of the AITE Research Center for SY 2022-2023.”</p>	<p>Unavailability of gathered funds</p> <p>Led the allocation of school funds to cover the needed budget for AY 2022-2023</p>	<p>Allocating School Fund</p>	<p>Filling-up the deficiencies or lack of gathered funds from the other sources of research resources</p>
--	---	-------------------------------	---

<p>“The unavailability of gathered funds from government grants and partnerships with other HEIs and NGOs has led the allocation of school funds to cover all the needed budget of the AITE Research Center for SY 2023-2024.”</p>	<p>Unavailability of gathered funds</p> <p>Led the allocation of school funds to cover the needed budget for AY 2023-2024</p>	<p>Allocating School Fund</p>	<p>Filling-up the deficiencies or lack of gathered funds from the other sources of research resources</p>
--	---	-------------------------------	---

Table 5.*Perspectives of AITE Research Center for Partnering with Other HEIs and NGOs*

Quotation	Codes	Subthemes	Themes
<p>“The AITE Research Center must open itself to partnership with other HEIs or even with NGOs who are willing to enter into a collaborative research activity.”</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open Collaborative 	<p>Partnering with HEIs and NGOs</p>	<p>Improved quality and productivity of research through collaboration</p>
<p>“ . . . it would bring a great help, not only financially but also institutionally and socially, if we can have ties and relationships with other organizations . . .”</p>	<p>Not only financially</p> <p>Ties and relationships with other organizations</p>	<p>Partnering with HEIs and NGOs</p>	<p>Ties and relationships with other HEIs and NGOs, aside from research</p>
<p>“Aside from expanding and contributing to knowledge research</p>	<p>Aside from expanding and contributing knowledge</p>	<p>Partnering with HEIs and NGOs</p>	<p>Ties and relationships with other HEIs and</p>

collaborations may also open further linkages between AITE and other HEIs and NGOs.”	Open further linkages		NGOs, aside from research
“We are therefore expecting that portion of the Research Budget for the upcoming school year, 2020-2021 will come from other stated Sources of Research Funds .. .”	Other stated sources of research funds	Partnering with HEIs and NGOs	Lessened management burden due to additional funds from partnership with other HEIs and NGOs

Table 6.

Perspectives of AITE Research Center for Applying for Government Grants

Quotation	Codes	Subthemes	Themes
“The AITE Research Center shall extend its efforts to apply and request for grants from government government	Extend its efforts Applying and requesting for grants from government agencies	Applying for Government Grant	Leveled-up quality of education through research with the support

agencies, especially those highly related in education.”			of the Government
“The fact that different government agencies offer and provide available funds for research activities to support HEIs must be taken advantage of by the Research Center.”	Government agencies Research Activities Support HEIs Taken Advantage	Applying for Government Grant	Leveled-up quality of education through research with the support of the Government
“. . . it would bring a great help, not only financially but also institutionally and socially, if we can have ties and relationships with other organizations . . .”	Not only financially Ties and relationships with other organizations	Applying for Government Grant	Opportunities from government regarding other aspects of higher education than research only
“This may open opportunities for grants not only in	Open opportunities	Applying for Government Grant	Opportunities from government regarding other

the field of research but in other areas of higher education of AITE as well.”	Not only in the field of research		aspects of higher education than research only
--	-----------------------------------	--	--

“We are therefore expecting that portion of the Research Budget for the upcoming school year, 2020-2021 will come from other stated Sources of Research Funds . . .”	Other stated sources of research funds	Applying for Government Grant	Lessened management burden due to additional funds from government grants
--	--	-------------------------------	---

“The fact that different government agencies offer and provide available funds for research activities to support HEIs must be taken advantage of by the Research Center.”	Different government agencies offer and provide available funds	Applying for Government Grant	Lessened management burden due to additional funds from government grants
	Support HEIs		

Model - Development Stage - Ultimately, after the documents of the AITE Research Center have been interpreted and analyzed, this paper, using the results of the textual analysis shall provide for a developed model of research resource generation in private higher education institution, representing the process of distillation and abstraction.

The process of distillation and abstraction is manifested in this stage, as the model developed involves the procedure of removing or taking out details to cut the characteristics into the essential ones alone (Wigmore, n.d.). As the model is developed after the textual analysis information and processes which are deemed dispensable have already been taken out. Removing the unnecessary details and portions of the procedures undertaken by the AITE Research Center was done after the careful consideration and analysis of the methods and process by the same.

CHAPTER V

Results and Discussion

The Research Resource Generation Practices of AITE-Research Center

Allocation of School Funds

“The school management takes it as a relevant step to allocate funds for the student, faculty and institutional researches to be conducted and published by the Center.”

(Memorandum No. SEL - 10 - 2019, August 13, 2019)

The analysis of the documents showed that the school management of AITE is fully supporting the AITE Research Center to conduct student, faculty and institutional research. And to that effect, it is going to allocate funds from its collection from the Tuition and Other Fees paid by the students. On the part of the management, this would be such a relevant step to allocate funds for the student, faculty and institutional research as it would even mean that the income of the school may be reduced or in one way or another compromised by such an allotment. In that regard, as well, in the process of allocating funds for the research undertaking, the school management, specifically the Finance and Accounting Department must set aside funds for the Annual Research Budgets to be appropriated for the programs of the Research Center.

“The allocation shall be sourced by AITE from the Tuition and Other Fees paid by the

students.” (Memorandum No. SEL - 10 - 2019, August 13, 2019)

As a Private HEI, AITE’s income depends highly on its collection of Tuition and Other Fees from its students. And so, in allocating school funds for the research endeavors of its research body, the AITE Research Center, the same collections of Tuition and Other Fees will be the very source of its contribution in the budget of the Research Center. As a matter of fact, AITE management is even willing to provide for funds for the Research Center to an extent beyond what is due from the R&D collections under its miscellaneous fees. This is in its pursuit towards improving research environment within the school community, and thus its readiness to spend a portion of its collections for other school programs for the Research Center’s sake.

“The amount to be allocated will be relative to the available school fees collected from the students.” (Memorandum No. SEL - 10 - 2019, August 13, 2019)

Given the school management’s allocation of school funds for the research activities of the AITE Research Center which will be sourced from the Tuition and other Fees paid for by the students, the school management also directs the Finance and Accounting Department to make sure that the amount of allocation will also be considering and will be relative to the total collection of the school fees for the School Year. While the management gives priority to the school it also emphasizes that it’s with certain limitations. Patently, it can obviously support its Research Center’s undertaking financially, but in no case shall it be beyond the total collections from Tuition and Other Fees. This is to give way for allocations to the other operational activities of the school as well.

“While our school provides for the deficiencies in the budget expected to have been sourced from outside parties . . .” (Memorandum No. SEL - 37 - 2020, May 30, 2020)

Likewise, while the AITE management pledges to support the research undertakings of the Research Center, it does not, however, proscribe it to *look for funding from outside sources* or to communicate and contact possible partners, sponsors or grantors for its research programs.

“The unavailability of gathered funds from government grants and partnership with other HEIs and NGOs has led the allocation of school funds to cover all the needed budget of the AITE Research Center.” (Annual Research Budget for 2019 - 2020)

The analysis of the documents also reveals that given that the school management is very much interested in expanding its research efforts, it is, therefore, willing to cover for all the shortages in financing the proposed budget of the AITE Research Center. Hence, even in the absence of funds from government agencies and partnerships with other HEIs and NGOs, the school management assures that the research activities of the Research Center will be financed, as its funds will be its primary source of generating funds.

Some of the experiences of the AITE Research Center revealed that some of the difficulties that led the management to ensure that even in the absence of funds from the other sources, it will still cover the necessary funding is the fact that external parties like other schools may be lacking in their own funding or financially incapable

to support their own research programs, hence their limitation to partner with other HEIs. As for NGOs and government agencies, they have set certain criteria or conditions, oftentimes in terms of areas of focus in choosing the HEI to which they shall award their grants. And so, to lessen the contingency that the Research Center's programs will be pending because of insufficiency of financial resources the school management is open in covering the necessary funding by allocating school funds, if truly needed be.

“The funds that will be derived from the allocation of school budget shall be at least 50% of the total fund requirement of the AITE Research Center.” (Memorandum No. SEL - 10 - 2019, August 13, 2019)

Based on the budget and plan of the AITE Research Center, as approved by the School President, the allocation of school fund for the research programs shall comprise at least fifty percent (50%) of the total budget of the Research Center. It is important to emphasize the words at least, which would, in effect, mean that it can be higher than 50% if indeed necessary or warranted by the circumstance.

Partnership with HEIs and other NGOs

Aside from Allocation of School Funds, the analysis of the documents reveals that the AITE Research Center has been in constant search for partnerships with other colleges and/or universities and even with NGOs in order to generate funds and financing for its research programs.

“The AITE Research Center must open itself to partnership with other HEIs or even with NGOs who are willing to enter into a collaborative research activity.”
(Memorandum No. SEL - 10 - 2019, August 13, 2019)

The school management has thus always enjoined and encouraged the AITE Research Center to open itself to partnerships with other HEIs and even with privately-established organizations, including those which are not-for-profit who may be willing to share and contribute to the research programs of the AITE Research Center. With this and through the efforts of the Research Center in engaging with other HEIs and NGOs, collaborative research may be jointly produced. The collaboration which is expected to commence through a sharing scheme in the financial resources of the AITE Research Center and that of its prospective partners will of course ignite and fuel for a smoother research and development journey for the parties.

“I would like to encourage you (Research Director) to extensively undertake efforts to enter into various communications with other HEIs, NGOs.....” (Memorandum No. SEL - 37 - 2020, May 30, 2020)

The school management's, specifically the School President's encouragement was actually to extensively undertake efforts to enter into various communications with other HEIs and NGOs. This is for the Research Center to be engaged in external-party partnerships. With this, it means that various communications are being given and endorsed by the Research Center to prospective partner HEIs and research-sponsoring NGOS. And with the efforts exerted by the AITE Research Center, the school management believes that the funding of its research programs and projects

will be augmented.

“Align and adjust the areas of priorities with the requirements and grant considerations of NGOs and government agencies.” (Minutes of Meeting, August 15, 2021 (Tuesday), 10:00am)

AITE’s management has also exhibited flexibility to carry out partnerships with NGOs. While it has already been conceived by the AITE Research Center that there are certain priorities that NGOs would like to research about and some or many of them do not align with its research priorities, the management has also encouraged the Research Center to make certain adjustments or include and consider the fields of interest of NGOs in its research thrust. It will hit two objectives then, one, is to obtain additional funding and the other is the fact that its research priorities will also be opened for expansion for other areas of study.

“. . . it would bring a great help, not only financially but also institutionally and socially, if we can have ties and relationships with other organizations . . .” (Memorandum No. SEL - 37 - 2020, May 30, 2020)

Moreover, an outset of research collaborations and partnerships in research activities of the AITE Research Center is considered as an opening for other prospective relationships with other HEIs and NGOs. It means that once a partnership starts in research projects, it can also give way for AITE to connect with outside parties in terms of scholarships, operational improvements, benchmarking and other academic and extracurricular collaborations. Hence, this kind of undertaking will not

only be helping the Research Center and the school financially but also institutionally and socially, since the relationship that may be built therefrom may open other partnerships in the different sectors of school and education.

“It is expected that at least 20% of the budget of the AITE Research Center will be generated from the partnerships, otherwise additional funds to set it off shall be generated from school funds allocation.” (Memorandum No. SEL - 10 - 2019, August 13, 2019)

The documents of the Research Center it is expected that at least 20% of the budget of the Research Center will be from the funding from the Partnership with other HEIs and NGOs. This is not but without *collatilla*, that if this will not be achieved, allocation of school funds will still be the primary source of the Research Center’s funds.

Application for Government Grants

“The AITE Research Center shall extend its efforts to apply and request for grants from government agencies, especially those highly related in education.” (Memorandum No. SEL - 10 - 2019, August 13, 2019)

The documents subjected to the analysis also disclosed that the AITE Research Center is not expected to depend only on the Allocation of School Funds, since as mentioned it may lead to certain compromise to the income generation of the school, as a Private Higher Education Institution. Likewise, since the availability of funds from

Partnerships with other HEIs and NGOs will also be dependent on the openness and financial capability of the prospective partners it is considered by the school management for AITE Research Center to look for other sources of research funding, this is why it is also encouraged by the school management to extend its efforts to apply and request for grants from government agencies especially those highly related in education.

“ . . . available research funding of government agencies such as Commission on Higher Education (CHED), Department of Science and Technology (DOST) and other government research-granting agencies.” (Minutes of Meeting, August 31, 2019 (Saturday), 3:00pm)

Different and various government agencies offer many grants for scholarships and research. Some of the research-grant giving bodies are the Commission on Higher Education (CHED), Department of Science and Technology (DOST), Department of Education and many else more. The presence of grants to be awarded by different government agencies is a huge opportunity to be grabbed by the Research Center.

“I would like to encourage you (Research Director) to extensively undertake efforts to enter into various communications with other HEIs, NGOs and even with sponsoring government agencies.” (Memorandum No. SEL - 37 - 2020, May 30, 2020).

Just like in partnership with other HEIs and NGOs, the School President, has also underscored the cheer for the Research Center to extensively undertake efforts

to enter into communication with various sponsoring government agencies. It can actually be done by constant and consistent inquiries and submission of viable qualifications to the different government offices offering grants for research programs. Browsing and identifying the agencies open to provide research sponsorships will also be very crucial to carry this practice out. Applications must also be made sure to be of quality to increase the possibility of becoming chose for research assistance and benefits

“Align and adjust the areas of priorities with the requirements and grant considerations of NGOs and government agencies.” (Minutes of Meeting, August 15, 2021 (Tuesday), 10:00am)

While, there are certain conditions and requirements to be complied with to qualify for the government grants, the Research Center is given the task to adjust and align its research priorities and thrusts if necessary and possible in order to get the chance of becoming awardees or beneficiaries of the offered government research grants. With this adjustment that the Research Center is willing to do, aside from generating funds from government grants, it can clearly give way for more government-related opportunities not just for the Research Center but for the entire school, as well.

“Whatever research grant will be received from government agencies will be distributed equally to the different programs of AITE, unless specified or intended by the granting agency.” (Memorandum No. SEL - 10 - 2019, August 13, 2019)

The school management also plans for the possible distribution of any grant that may be sourced from government agencies' grants. An equal distribution of the grants that may possibly be given by the government offices to AITE Research Center among the programs of AITE shall be done, except when the government agency particularly identifies the specific program to be awarded with the grant.

“It is expected that at least 30% of the budget of the AITE Research Center will come from Government Grants, otherwise additional funds to set it off shall be generated from school fund allocation.” (Memorandum No. SEL - 10 - 2019, August 13, 2019)

The AITE Research Center sets a thirty percent (30%) cap of its total budget to be generated from government grants. But, just like in partnership with other HEIs and NGOs, since this is subject to the availability and awarding of grants, the school management will also be ready to cover any deficiency in funds from grants from government agencies.

The Perspectives Underlying the Research Resource Generation Practices of AITE Research Center

Perspectives for Allocating School Funds

Based on the analysis of the documents the perspectives that lead to the allocation of school funds to the research activities of AITE are: (a) the indispensable role of research in the development and learning of students and (b) filling-up the deficiencies or lack of gathered funds from the other sources of research resources like (i) partnership with other HEIs and NGOs and (ii) government grants.

Indispensable Role of Research in the Development and Learning of Students

“The allotment of funds will be done in order to foster a research-conducive environment for students and faculty members alike.” (Minutes of Meeting, August 31, 2019 (Saturday), 3:00pm)

AITE management recognizes the indispensable role of research in the development and learning of the students. In the spirit of this appreciation of the part that research is undertaking in students' progress the school management is more than willing to allocate funds to support and finance the programs and projects of its research activities. The allotment of funds will be done in order to foster a research-conducive environment for students and faculty members alike.

“The Asian Institute of Technology and Education (AITE), at the peak of its aims, intently includes in the pursuit of its mission to strive to develop the full potentials of its students and help them become achievers in their chosen fields, the role and maximization of research and development” (Memorandum No. SEL - 10 - 2019, August 13, 2019)

The honing of the students' abilities remains at the peak of AITE's aims and of every single HEI, and this perspective serves as one of the explanations for the AITE management's allocation of school funds to the Research Center's undertakings. The realization that HEIs, including AITE perform triple function of instruction, research and extension suffices in pushing the AITE management to allocate school funds for the

its research body. It is the belief of AITE that with the strengthening of its research programs it will be able to help the students to become achievers in the chosen fields through maximizing the function that research serves in higher education.

Filling-Up the Deficiency or Lack of Funds from the Other Sources of Research Resources

“Given the unavailability of funds from other sources than school fund allocation, it is hereby ordered for the Accounting and Finance Department to set aside the funds [for] the Annual Research Budget for. . .” (Memorandum No. SEL – 43 – 2020, October 20, 2020)

Another point of view that leads the AITE management to allocate school funds to the Research Center’s projects and programs is to fill up or cover the lack in or unavailability of gathered funds from other sources of research resources. As mentioned earlier in the paper since the partnership with other HEIs and NGOs and awarding of government grants highly depend on the conditions, requirements and availability of funds from external parties, there can be no full assurance that big amounts of funds or at the very least funds will be generated therefrom. Hence, it leads the AITE management to ensure that any deficiency in the expected funds from those other sources will be shouldered by the allocation of school funds. With this, the Finance and Accounting Department is instructed to set aside or allocate funds for the annual program of activities of the Research Center.

Perspectives for Partnering with other HEIs and NGOs

The analysis of the documents revealed three perspectives of why AITE Research Center pushes itself to be open to partnership with other HEIs and NGOs. Firstly, the AITE Research Center wants to come up with improved quality and productivity of research through collaboration. Another perspective is that AITE Research Center wants to build up ties and relationships with other colleges and universities and NGOs which are not limited only to research. Lastly, the AITE Research Center is in continuous efforts to be in collaboration with other schools and NGOs because the funds to be generated from those partnerships with other HEIs and NGOs will lessen the burden of the management by augmenting or adding up with the funds from school allocations.

Improved Quality and Productivity of Research through Collaboration

“The AITE Research Center must open itself to partnership with other HEIs or even with NGOs who are willing to enter into a collaborative research activity.”
(Memorandum No. SEL - 10 - 2019, August 13, 2019)

The AITE Research Center believes that openness for partnership with other HEIs and NGOs can kindle collaborative research. And with the research raising from collaborations, both quality and productivity of the partners may be improved. The willingness of other HEIS and NGOs to be engaged in these partnerships must be availed of by the Research Center. With respect to collaborative research, it shall refer to the sharing of financial resources, and may also even include exchange of experts and opinions in the creation of the research outputs.

Ties and Relationships with other HEIs and NGOs, aside from Research

“ . . . it would bring a great help, not only financially but also institutionally and socially, if we can have ties and relationships with other organizations . . .” (Memorandum No. SEL - 37 - 2020, May 30, 2020)

Another perspective that the AITE Research Center is invoking in its endeavor to partner with other HEIs and with NGOs is to have relationships or ties with other organizations and expand such relationships not just with respect to research but also into the other different aspects of higher education. The partnership may benefit not only the Research Center but the entire AITE. Once a relationship is put up through research collaborations, other HEIs and NGOs may open their doors as well for other joint activities which are not necessarily financial in character. An example probably is the conduct of seminars with faculty members from each other being the sharers or speakers. NGOs on the other hand may invite students of AITE to be engaged in their efforts and causes, either under internship or out of school affairs. It is the viewpoint of the Research Center that a harmonious relationship must begin somewhere else, and in this case, research collaborations may be that door.

Lessened Management Burden due to Additional Funds from Partnership with Other HEIs and NGOs

“We are therefore expecting that portion of the Research Budget for the upcoming school year will come from other stated Sources of Research Funds . . .”

(Memorandum No. SEL - 37 - 2020, May 30, 2020)

Research funds of the AITE Research Center may be said to primarily come from the allocation of school funds. However, while the school management is more than willing to provide for the necessary funds, the AITE Research Center would like to lessen the burden of the management. Hence, its efforts to be in partnership with other schools and with NGOs. Funds to be accumulated from these partnerships will certainly be useful and beneficial as it will serve as additional funding for the Research Center and will augment the budget from school allocations. As another source of research resources the collaborations will, amongst others, be able to financially help the AITE Research Center to carry out its research programs and undertakings. With this, in mind the AITE Research Center exert the best of its efforts to engage in these partnerships.

Perspectives for Applying for Government Grants

The AITE Research Center strives to be able to avail the government grants for research of the different agencies because of the following perspectives, to wit: (1) it wants to take advantage of the government's initiatives to help HEIs in their research projects leading to a leveled-up quality of education, (2) the opportunities and benefits offered by the government to HEIs with respect to the other aspects of higher education, and (3) to augment the allocation of school funds causing lesser burden on the part of the management.

Leveled -Up Quality of Education through Research with the Support of the

Government

“The fact that different government agencies offer and provide available funds for research activities to support HEIs must be taken advantage of by the Research Center.” (Memorandum No. SEL - 10 - 2019, August 13, 2019)

Undeniably, many government agencies offer and provide for research grants and scholarships. CHED, DepEd, and DOST to name a few are examples of government offices which have been in full support to HEI’s research endeavors. As such, the AITE Research Center seeks and applies for these government grants to take advantage of the initiatives that the government is offering. The AITE Research Center and the government find a vertex in aspiring to improve and level up the quality of education for the students, especially through research. The opportunities posed by the government agencies must be maximized by the Research Center. This is even up to the point when the management even suggested the Research Center to align its research thrusts and priorities to that of the grant-giving government agencies.

Opportunities from Government Agencies regarding the Other Aspects of Higher Education than Research only

“This may open opportunities for grants not only in the field of research but in other areas of higher education of AITE as well.” (Memorandum No. SEL - 10 - 2019, August 13, 2019)

Other government agencies do not limit their grants in research projects only. There are many of those government offices which along with research grants also offer scholarship grants, financial assistance, trainings, and seminars. Another perspective that explains the AITE Research Center's extensive application for government grants is to give way for these benefits and relationships to be entered into and availed of by the Research Center and the school as a whole. Since government agencies' intention to support education more expansively their education projects and support programs extend to other aspects of higher education also. The proactive exertions of the government entice the AITE Research Center to build up relationships with its various and different agencies.

Lessened Management Burden due to Grants from Government Agencies

“We are therefore expecting that portion of the Research Budget for the upcoming school year will come from other stated Sources of Research Funds . . .”
(Memorandum No. SEL - 37 - 2020, May 30, 2020)

Lastly, funds that may be obtained from the grants awarded by the different government agencies will augment the allocation of school funds. This inspires the AITE Research Center more to be consistent in its efforts to apply for government grants. Similar with partnership and other HEIs and NGOs, the funds to be gathered from the awards of grants from government agencies will help to decrease the amount of allocation of school funds, as it will mean smaller amounts of deficiencies to be answered by school funds. As a matter of perspective, this is probably the most practical one, especially on the part of the AITE Research Center.

Model of Research Resource Generation

The following model, which is developed after the careful analysis of the documents is proposed for Private HEIs.

PRIVATE HEI'S RESEARCH RESOURCE GENERATION PRACTICES AND UNDERLYING PERSPECTIVES			ORGANIZATIONAL STRATEGIES
Allocation of School Funds			ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT
<i>Indispensable Role of Research in the Development and Learning of the Students</i>	<i>Filling-Up the Deficiency or Lack of Funds from Partnership with other HEIs and NGOs and Government Grants</i>		
Application for Government Grants			INSTITUTIONAL ORIENTATION
<i>Leveled-Up Quality of Education through Research with Government Support</i>	<i>Opportunities from Government Agencies regarding the other Aspects of Higher Education</i>	<i>Lessened Management Burden due to Additional Funds from Grants from Government</i>	
Partnership with other HEIs and NGOs			EXTERNAL RELATIONS
<i>Improved Quality and Productivity of Research through Collaboration</i>	<i>Ties and Relationships, with other HEIs and NGOs, aside from Research</i>	<i>Lessened Management Burden due to Additional Funds from Partnership with other HEIs and NGOs</i>	

Figure 2. Matrix of Organizational Strategies on Research Resource Generation.

The model developed based on the results of the study shows the Matrix of Organizational Strategies on Research Resource Generation. The strategies were derived from the practices and underlying perspectives of the AITE-Research Center. The strategies formed are the following: (1) Organizational Commitment, (2) Institutional Orientation and (3) External Relations,

Organizational Commitment

Based on the matrix the research resource generation practice of allocating funds to the research activities of the RDO, which can be explained by the role of research and the filling-up of deficiency in gathered funds from other sources provide for Organizational Commitment as a Research Resource Generation strategy.

As mentioned by Calma (2010), funding support for research activities may come from internal sources or those school-set allocations through research offices, which is available for application by any of the researchers in the college or university. It also agrees with the position of the AITE Research Center, as he clearly observed that private HEIs have been dependent on the fees paid for by the students while other considerations are also taken into account on how to the schools may be funded by other sources (Calma, 2010). This only goes to show that the methodological experience of AITE Research Center whereby it generates its research resources, specifically financing, from its own school funds or those collected from its students is shared by the other HEIs.

This support of the school management to the AITE Research Center may be

said to primarily be anchored on the research functions of an HEI. As put by Quitaras and Abuso (2021), the three functions of colleges and universities include instruction, extension and research. From this idea, the school management derives its inclusion on its priority the advancement of its research undertakings, even to the point of allocating funds generated from the tuition fees of the students, which were primarily intended to be used for other purposes, which was also mentioned by Calma (2010), when he said that private and public universities fund their operations, including research operations, through their present funding resources – which in the case of AITE may specifically refer to tuition and other collected fees.

As clearly put by Azim (2020), research helps students to open doors for learning and growth, likewise it promotes and protects memory and develops problem-solving abilities. Research also teaches students to respond to issues and questions and even problems that have not yet been resolved or known by others, this is along with its impact which led students to be curious and taps students' analytical skills. Given these benefits and many else more, AITE believes that the empowerment and funding of its Research Center will be necessary. As a Higher Education, it realizes the role that research plays in the honing of the potentials of the students. This is one of the points that explain why the school management is willing to provide for the funds for the research activities of its Research Center.

On the other end, while there may be other sources of research resources, they depend on the intention and condition of the external parties, hence the possibility that for a certain period, funds from such other sources may not be available. Certain reasons for the insufficiency of gathered funds from other sources include that which

was stated in Clemeña and Acosta (2007) that one of the reasons that explains that lack in the funds of HEIs, not just of AITE but other private HEIs, for research projects, is the fact, indeed, that they highly depend on students' payments of tuition fees as their primary source of revenue. With this, the limitation in the institutional funds may hamper other HEIs to engage with research partnerships. While, as put by Calma (2010), government agencies such as the DOST provides support for research in specific areas of priority through its different agencies. This may lead to the Research Center's failure to gather funds from government grants if its priority areas do not align with that of the granting agency. And so, in such cases, given the ideal of AITE about the importance of research for its students, the school management is even willing to cover for the deficiencies or shortages in the gathered funds from other sources. This is anchored from the policy of the school management that in support to the Research Center's research undertakings, all deficiencies in the funds to finance its budgeted activities, the school management will cover it through its collected funds from the students under tuition fees and other miscellaneous fees, although such allocation is not necessarily covered by those fees.

In the context of Research and Development Management, allocating funds to the projects which form part of the activities of the RDO and the prioritization of such research and development projects reflect the organizational commitment as a strategy in overseeing Research and Development. The fact that an organization, or RDO, for that matter is willing to provide for funding in order to fulfill the function of research and development and to self-sufficiently cover for all shortages in the funding from other possible sources are immensely manifesting of the RDO's commitment to its objectives. While risk is present in allocating funds to the extent which may be

beyond to what is budgeted or expected, the organization's commitment makes it sure that an RDOs goal of producing research is achieved.

Institutional Orientation

Aside from organizational commitment, institutional orientation may be said to be a strategy of RDOs in generating research resources. Institutional orientation may be emphasized through application for government grants.

The availability of research grants from government agencies is proven by Qitoras and Abuso (2021), when he said that there are universities which research outputs are outcomes of partnerships with other HEIs and with financial support from different government agencies which include the CHED, DOST and the National Research Center of the Philippines (NRCP). The hope of the school management that the AITE Research Center will be able to gather funds from government grants is also supported by the study of Zhu and Lou (2011), where they have alluded that government must be a major funding source for higher education. On the same study they continued that one of the functions of the government, education-wise, is to prioritize HEIs or areas of study which are primarily involved in research. Likewise, Calma (2010) made mention of the fact that outside financing sources for utilization in research of HEIs include international and local government agencies. He also highlighted that CHED provides for competitive grants, which are available to be applied by any researcher from private and public HEIs, including the grant-in-aid and the block grants. Therefore, the school management's pursuit of generating funds from government grants is actually justified and could have been really possible to support

its Research Center's undertakings and projects.

According to Agile Marketing Education (2023), in funding research the government shares big part to research activities both in private and public schools, including HEIs. Available research grants offered by different agencies of the governments are not minimal things to be disregarded by the AITE Research Center. This is why it makes sure that there is a continuous effort for it to apply for funding as sponsored by the government. The center and the school management believe that the initiatives and efforts of the government to participate through financially supporting research endeavors among universities and colleges should be taken advantage of. With the availability of research grants it can be viewed that there is a commonality in the appreciation of the government and the AITE Research Center with respect to the role of research and development. As discussed by Rapple (2019), policy-makers in the government would like to know if they can base their decisions and policies on government-funded studies. Hence, the more that the government initiates in supporting and providing grants for different research activities, including those from the academia.

Another perspective that may be viewed on why the Research Center continuously applies for government grants is its intention to build up relationship with different government agencies in the different aspects of higher education and not only in terms of research. Gumban (2013), mentioned that the government's willingness to be in partnership with HEIs is led by its necessity for a means to carry out development projects which are more often delivered effectively by universities and colleges. The openness of the government to be in relationship with HEIs is wanted to be maximized

by the Research Center. The availability of grants from government may not only be limited to supporting research activities but may also extend to scholarships and many else more. Something important, relevant and helpful to the AITE not just as a Research Center but as an HEI.

Just like the funds which may be generated from partnership with other HEIs and NGOs, grants that may be received from government agencies would be highly helpful for AITE in funding its Research Center. Patently, with the funds derived from government grants lesser shouldering of financing deficiency will have to be done by the school management, hence it can save more for its other aspects of operations. Once more, it is enlightening to note the point of Clemeña and Acosta (2007) that private HEIs highly depend only with its primary source of income which is tuition fees paid for by their enrollees. Therefore, any additional funds that may be externally generated will benefit the many operational and academic sections of AITE including its Research Center.

Applications for government grants which can be explained by an RDOs continuous desire to achieve its goals and to grab the opportunities posed by different government agencies and to lessen the burden that the organization's management will have to bear, hugely represents institutional orientation. Institutional orientation for that matter and as a strategy may refer to the organizations or institution's awareness and consciousness as to its needs and how such needs may be responded to and fulfilled. An RDO which is fully aware of its needs must also be in full knowledge of its capacity to comply with such needs. In the context of research and development management, an RDO is familiar of the fact that there is a standing necessity for it to

generate resources and that without sufficient resources, its projects and undertakings may not be completed and pursue. While organizational commitment reflects a self-sufficient and self-reliant strategy on research resource generation, it does not eliminate the reality, however, that institutional funds of an RDO may not be unlimited and subject to certain constraints, thus the need to gather funds from government grants that may augment that organization's allocation. The application for government grants realizes the institutionally-oriented strategy which means to say that given the awareness of the RDO to the limitation of its budget and the impelling importance of its functions, then it seeks to generate resources or funds from sources other than organizational allocation to its projects and activities.

External Relations

Lastly, aside from organizational commitment and institutional orientation, another strategy that may be derived from this study is External Relations. To gather resources, it is important not to contain the opportunities only to institutional dimension or the government grants. As the function of research is common and inclusive in various and many organizations, it shall be considered as a strategy to generate research resources the relationships that may be built with other institutions.

Partnership with other HEIs to produce research outcomes may be called as collaborative research. Quitoras and Abuso (2021) amplified that collaboration is important in raising research going to the next level. In his study, it was also found out that other schools encourage their instructors, of all ranks, not just to create their own research work in their areas of expertise but to likewise enter into collaboration. And

this collaboration should not be limited only to those from the same schools but also with other universities and colleges. This represents the AITE's intention to be engaged with other HEIs in multiple facets of collaborative research from financing into the division of labor. As put by Sprunger (2017), the connection allows harmonies that push toward innovation and discovery. Quitoras and Abuso (2021) also shared that in one university the lack of funds is being set off by external financing. The possible partnership with other HEIs as eyed by the school management may open doors not only for research resources but also for other academic and extra-curricular collaborations.

On the other hand, partnership to which AITE Research Center may not only be limited to other HEIs. It can also have collaborations with NGOs that look for research providing institutions like itself. As observed by Calma (2010), foundations, private companies and corporations sometimes make investments in education – which include research. This could be an opportunity for AITE Research Center to benefit from these grants or investments that organizations not affiliated to the government may be giving away. The possibility of the collaboration between AITE Research Center as an HEI and the NGOs is based on the observation of Tylzanowski et al. (2023), wherein HEIs have become more highly inclined in the social arena, hence playing a contributory part in social development, on which they intersect with NGOs in terms of purpose.

Another reason visible for the efforts of the AITE Research Center to be in partnership with other HEIs and NGOs is to build wider relationships that may start from and that will not just be limited only with research financing and projects but in

many other aspects of higher education. Oleta (2024), mentioned that efforts to and initiatives to strengthen partnership with other HEIs in the Philippines expand and widen an HEI's educational connections and networks towards inclusive development through partnerships, co-creation and collaboration.

Finally, but probably most practical amongst the perspectives of the Research Center in pursuing partnerships with other HEIs and NGOs is the fact that successful partnerships would mean additional funds for the Research Center to carry out its research projects and programs. With this, funds allocated by the school will be augmented and that the school management will not have to cover so much for the research undertakings of the center. As likewise put by Calma (2010), other private HEIs are able to add up additional funds for its institutional allocations through external funding. And this is what AITE wants to happen, that its school allocation will be added up with supporting funds from outside parties, including collaborations with other HEIs and NGOs.

The external relationship that is achieved through collaboration with other organizations which are willing to provide resources to the RDO is a huge opportunity as well for the RDO to gather the necessary amount of funding that will support its research projects and undertakings. This strategy of building strong external relations may not only be limited to sharing of financial resources but may even extend to human resources development in the context of trainings and exchanged of knowledge and information.

CHAPTER VI

RESEARCH SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Research Summary

Research and Development has been becoming one of the biggest highlights of tertiary or collegiate education, which is being fostered by the Asian Institute of Technology and Education, and of its research body the AITE Research Center. And just like any aspect of any process, research and development also requires resources to finance its projects and programs. Given the importance of resources in research activities of a higher education institution, this study dug deep to understand the research resource generation practices of higher education institution and the perspectives that underlie such ways and methods. It also aspired to develop and propose a model on research resource generation that may be useful in the context of private higher education institutions.

Using ethnomethodology, this study sought to know the practices of the AITE Research Center in generating its research resources and the perspectives that tend to explain such practices. The data used and analyzed to answer the questions of the study were derived from the pertinent documents of the AITE Research Center. The methods, ways, means and practices of the Research Center were analyzed and observed based on the documents which include school memoranda, minutes of meetings and other relevant papers like approved budgets.

In order to obtain the data, the researcher initially wrote a request letter to the

School President of the Asian Institute of Technology and Education, asking its permission to have a copy of, use and analyze its memoranda, minutes of meetings and other related documents to its Research Center's activities and programs. The school management, through the signature of the School President granted the request of the researcher. Copies of the said documents were then obtained by the researcher and began the textual analysis of the documents to understand the practices and the perspectives that explain them as to the Research Center's resource generation.

In the analysis, the excerpts in the documents were thematically viewed upon. Quotations from the documents which represent and manifest the practices of the Research Center were taken. From the excerpts codes were extracted to encapsulate the meaning which inspire the practices and perspectives presented in the documents. From these codes, categories or subthemes and more specifically, themes were generated. This thematizing aided the understanding of the meanings that emanate from the issued documents as to the methods and ways and perspectives of the Research Center in generating its research resources.

Based on the results of the study, the research resource generation practices of the Asian Institute of Technology and Education Research Center are, allocation of school funds, partnership with other HEIs and NGOs and application for government grants.

The school management is willing to allocate funds from its tuition fee collections to the research activities of the AITE Research Center. Likewise, allocation of school funds happens whenever there is any deficiency from the other sources of

research funding. The Research Center has also been encouraged by the school management to continuously endeavor to be in partnership with other schools or even with non-government organizations which are willing to enter into collaborations in producing research works. There are also available grants which are offered by different government agencies, and these are sought to be availed of by the AITE Research Center.

There are different perspectives that explain each research resource generation practice of the AITE Research Center. As can be derived from the results of the study, the school management is willing to provide the funds of the AITE Research Center primarily because of its realization that research plays an indispensable role in the development and learning of its. It believes and supports that an HEI is not only tasked to perform the function of instruction in honing the potentials of its students but also to engage them in research activities. Given this well-accepted tenet by AITE about the contribution of research in the development of students' potentials, the school management is even willing to fill-up or cover the deficiency and lack in the funds which are supposed to be generated by the Research Center from other possible sources, namely: (1) partnership with other HEIs and NGOs and (2) application for government grants. In short, in the absence of funds generated from the two other sources, the school funds will finance the targeted budget of the Center.

The school management has also been very emphatic in encouraging and reminding the Research Center to have communications and to strive to be in partnership with other HEIs and NGOs. It is driven by the Research Center's belief that partnership with other HEIs and NGOS will lead for it to come up with collaborative

research that bring an improved quality and productivity of research. Collaborative research refers to those which are produced through the collaborative efforts and resources of HEIs. These partnerships are viewed by the Research Center to be important as this will be augmenting to the funds that the school may allocate for its research projects. The partnerships sought for these partnerships as it will lead to additional financing or lesser burden on the part of the management that can be beneficial to the activities of the Research Center. Finally, the Research Center is also pushed to be in partnership with other HEIs and even with NGOs as this may open ties and relationships which are not limited only to research undertakings and financial or resource collaborations.

From the results of the study, it can be viewed that the perspectives that explain the Research Center's practice to apply for the grants offered by different government agencies include the additional funding that may be generated from these grants. To be given the grant for a research project from certain government agencies would mean a big help to the school management as it would augment the funds that it would allocate and it will reduce the burden and deficiency in funding from other sources that it will have to shoulder. The Research Center also believes that the existence of these grants should not be disregarded, hence one of the reasons why it is intending to avail them is to grab the chance fostered by the government to level up the quality of education through providing grants to research projects, upon compliance to their conditions. With the grants available, it signifies that the government agencies are open to be in relation and communication with HEIs, thus, the Research Center's intention as well to build up relationship with these government agencies to take the opportunities and benefits not only with respect to research activities but with other

aspects of higher education that may be improved by such a relationship.

A model was developed which considered the most relevant and observed features of the practice of the AITE Research Center. To generate research funds the model proposed that communications with external parties must first be undertaken, with this the Research Center will be able to know if there are funds available from outside parties which will augment to the allocation of school funds. While in case there is no fund generated from outside parties, then the Research Center will simply request for the allocation of school funds. When the funds have been gathered, a budget distribution and allocation of it to the different research programs and projects of the research center may already be done. After allocation of the available funds have been made, the release and liquidation of the funds may also be done, provided there is a regular reporting of the disbursement made is accomplished. The model suggested has included only those procedures and steps which are necessary and indispensable in the generation up to the succeeding process of research resources.

Conclusions

Similar to Public HEIs, Private HEIs, have well shown that it can generate funds either internally or externally. Research units of PHEIs find remedy in the insufficiency of funds from outside sources. It only goes to show that Private HEIs just like any other HEIs are also open to communicate and undertake activities with other institutions to achieve its goals and to raise additional funding. However, given the realized importance of research in the development and learning of its learners, Private HEIs are willing to solely finance the research projects of its research unit, subject to certain

conditions intended not to compromise the other operational activities of the institution, if external funding is not feasible.

.

The results of the study likewise showed that private HEIs agree that problems may arise due to lack of funds and resources, including in the area of research and development. Further, while there is no specific rule or standard on how funds are to be used in the field of education, the Private HEIs manifested its subscription in the direct relationship between availability of funding and the research productivity. Private HEIs, based on the analysis of the data, have shown priority and attention on its research and development function by assuring that it will be able to produce research outputs to be financed by resources generated from different sources.

Furthermore, it has been established that research has become more significant and compelling during this era, thus, it is actually and highly important for activities relating thereto to be funded with sufficient resources as this is the appropriate time to prioritize research. Given that research plays a pivotal role in the education of every HEI's stakeholders, the practice of ensuring that the research programs and projects are funded with appropriate and adequate amounts of funds have been well done by Private HEIs.

The study sheds light as to the appreciation of Private HEIs on research resource generation which, in many ways, is similar to how other Higher Education Institutions practice their own acquisition of resources. One significant aspect of resource generation in terms of research, however, which seems to be unique in Private HEIs, is its management's willingness to provide for funding beyond what is expected of it if

generated funds from other sources will be lacking. This intention and prioritization of the school management of Private HEIs would seem to deviate on the usual custom of appropriate or targeted distribution of funds among its different operational activities. Nevertheless, given that it takes research and development to be of immense importance, is its willingness to take the risk and hope for progress not only as an institution but more over for its learners.

As the study shown, resource generation is a mandate of Higher Education Institutions, even on the part of private ones. It has also been established that the functions of HEIs, including PHEIs, extend to research and development. Hence, Private HEIs take research resource generation as indispensable and highly necessary in its operations and in the continuity of its development and progress. Private HEIs have also confirmed that the management and control of resources lead to efficiency and effectiveness in meeting the organization's objectives.

Recommendations

Future Studies

The limited literatures regarding research resource generation, specifically, in the context of Private Higher Education Institutions call the conduct of this study. As it appears from the results of the study, PHEIs often depend solely on their own resources generated from tuition and other fees. This does not however limit the schools to gather funds from external sources like other HEIs, NGOs and even from government agencies.

It is suggested to likewise investigate on the impact of partnerships with other HEIs on the research productivity of an HEI. Since, as revealed from this study, partnerships with HEIs are inclined to develop collaborative research it would be a reasonable of point of interest to be able to understand if, indeed, research partnerships with other schools make a school more able to create and publish more studies and higher quality of research.

Another point that may be focused on in succeeding studies is the impact of research grants in an HEI's research performance. The question on the effects of the joint forces of HEIs and government initiatives is something that is also worth to be looked for. The availability of government grants and the opportunity that it fosters for HEIs is immensely beneficial for the availing and awarded colleges and universities. However, it is also worthy to ponder if the utilization of grants from government agencies, research-wise, improves the quality of outputs and results of the HEI.

This study focused primarily on the generation of research resources, nevertheless, it would be a probable topic of interest to study the manner generated funds are being utilized by HEIs. By dealing with this possible topic of study a continuity in understanding how resources are generated and how those accumulates resources are being used may be established.

Practical Recommendations

Given the results of the study and the answers to the questions of the research

recommendations are being put forward to the different expected beneficiaries of the paper. Firstly, it is suggested to the AITE Research Center and school management to continue exerting its effort to generate funds and more financial resources from the other sources of research resources like partnership with other HEIs and NGOs and in applying for government grants. Hence, it is highly recommended for the AITE Research Center to adopt its strategy to align its research thrust with that of the requirements of NGOs and government agencies in order to generate more research funding.

While for other Private Higher Education Institutions, it is proposed to adopt the model developed through this study in generating research resources, as it is flexible and open for collaboration with external parties. The model being recommended recognizes opportunities to augment research funding other than that would come only from the allocation of school funds or those funds collected by the schools from the tuition fees of the students.

REFERENCES

- Acido, J. V., & Kilongkilong, D. A. (2022). Resource Management Practices of a Public Higher Education Institution in the Philippines.
- Adams, J. D., & Griliches, Z. (1998). Research productivity in a system of universities. *Ann Econ Stat*, 49- 50, 127-162.
- Azim, A. (2020, August 11). *15 Common Reasons: Why is Research Important for Students*. Retrieved from AssignmentHelp: <https://www.assignmenthelp.ae/blog/15-common-reasons-why-is-research-important-for-students/#:~:text=The%20whole%20process%20of%20research,of%20learning%20and%20literary%20growth.&text=Studies%20reveal%20that%20research%20helps,understanding%20of%20concep>.
- Bua, F. T., & Adzongo, P. I. (2014). Impact of financial management on secondary school's administration in zone a senatorial district of Benue State-Nigeria. *Public Policy and Administration Research*, 95-103.
- Calma, A. (July 2010). Funding For Research and Research Training and Its Effects on Research Activity: The Case of the Philippines. *The Asia Pacific Education Researcher*, 213-228.
- CHED. (2016). *Roadmap Public Higher Education Reform*. Quezon City, Philippines: CHED.
- Clemeña, R. S., & Acosta, S. A. (n.d.). Developing Research Culture in Philippine Higher Education Institutions: Perspectives of University Faculty.
- Corssman, A. (2019, January 06). *The Definition and Function of Ethnomethodology*. Retrieved from ThoughtCo.: <https://www.thoughtco.com/ethnomethodology->
- Research Resource Generation in Higher Education: Practices of A Private Institution 91

- Hak, T. (1992). Psychiatric records as transformations of other texts. *Text in Context: Contributions to Ethnomethodology*, 138-155.
- Hausman, N. (2021). University innovation and local economic growth. *Review of Economics and Statistics*.
- Heritage, J. (1996). *Garfinkel and Ethnomethodology*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Heritage, J. (1998). Harold Garfinkel. *Key Sociological Thinkers*, 175-188.
- Jackson, C. K., Johnson, R. C., & Persico, C. (2016). The effects of school spending on educational and economic outcomes: evidence from school finance reforms. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 157-218.
- Khan, A. (2023, October 19). *Textual Analysis: Definition, Approaches and Examples*. Retrieved from lettria: https://www.lettria.com/blogpost/textual-analysis-definition-approaches-and-examples?fbclid=IwZXh0bgNhZW0CMTEAAAR37orSxF0j8eL-jm45SF1i7a3iID_iUkS_rX5wLReSkOghiUhHTNjkh7wc_aem_AeY0t5rByhX0YTGcgUzltR6HciUGgnq_mCiMHYAq0_AqKmvdh3EYF4f1z-tcCCIQUkr8B0XEoc8GpJit6-
- Lehn, D. V. (2014). *Harold Garfinkel: The Creation and Development of Ethnomethodology*. Walnut Creek, CA: Left Coast Press Inc.
- Leiter, K. (1980). *A Primer on Ethnomethodology*. New York, NY: Oxford University Press.
- Lynch, M. (2009). Ethnomethodology and history: documents and the production of history.
- Maglakelidze, Giogobiani, & Shukakidze. (2013). School Funding in Georgia. *Eric.ed.gov*.
- Mbaleka, S. W. (2015). Factors leading to limited faculty publications on Philippine higher education institutions.

- Nnebedum, C., & Egboka, P. (2017). Analysis of Resource Management Strategies Adopted by Principals for Secondary Schools Improvement in Enugu State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Advance Research and Innovative Ideas in Education*, 4124-4129.
- Oleta, A. V. (2024, July 8). *UPLB strengthens partnerships with HEIs in the PH*. Retrieved from UPLB: <https://uplb.edu.ph/all-news/uplb-strengthens-partnerships-with-heis-in-the-ph/>.
- Pillay, R. (2019, January 13). *Ethnomethodology*. Retrieved from Springer Link: https://link.springer.com/referenceworkentry/10.1007/978-981-10-5251-4_68
- Pollner, M., & Emerson, R. (2001). Ethnomethodology and Ethnography. *Handbook of Ethnography*, 118- 135.
- Quitoras, M. L., & Abuso, J. E. (2021). Best Practices of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) for the Development of Research Culture in the Philippines. *Pedagogical Research*.
- Sprunger, J. G. (2017, November 30). *The Benefits of Engaging in Collaborative Research Relationships*. Retrieved from Association for Psychological Science: <https://www.psychologicalscience.org/observer/the-benefits-of-engaging-in-collaborative-research-relationships>.
- Thelwall, M., Simrick, S., Viney, I., & den Besselaar, P. (2023). What is research funding, how does it influence research, and how is it recorded? Key dimensions of variation. *Scientometrics*, 6085- 6106.
- Trace, C. B. (2016). Ethnomethodology: Foundational insights on the nature and meaning of documents in everyday life. *Journal of Documentation*, 47-64.
- Tria, J. Z. (2020). The covid-19 pandemic through the lens of education in the Philippines: The new normal. *International Journal of Pedagogical*

Development and Lifelong Learning, 1-5.

Tylzanowski, R., Schirmacher, M., Uude, K., & Lobacz, K. (2023). Success factors and barriers to digital co-creation between HEIs and NGOs. *Procedia Computer Science*, 4254-4263.

Ulla, M. (2017). Teacher Training in Myanmar: Teachers' Perceptions and Implications. *International Journal of Instruction*, 103-118.

Ulla, M. B. (2018). Benefits and challenges of doing research: Experiences from Philippine public school teachers. *Issues in Educational Research*, 797-810.

Wigmore, I. (n.d.). *Abstraction*. Retrieved from TechTarget: [https://www.techtarget.com/whatis/definition/abstraction#:~:text=Abstraction%20\(from%20the%20Latin%20abs,a%20set%20of%20essential%20characteristics](https://www.techtarget.com/whatis/definition/abstraction#:~:text=Abstraction%20(from%20the%20Latin%20abs,a%20set%20of%20essential%20characteristics).

Yizengaw, J. Y., Agegnehu, M. A., & Ehmke, T. (2021). Practices and challenges of school financial resource management implementation in Bahir Dar City administration of Ethiopia: A comparative study between government and private secondary schools. *Cogent Education*.

Zhu, H., & Lou, S. (2011). Marketization of higher education. *Chandos Asian Studies Series*, 67-102.